

**DOES INTRINSIC MOTIVATION INFLUENCE EMPLOYEE AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT
DURING DIGITAL CHANGE?**

**THE ROLE OF JOB CHARACTERISTICS AND EMPLOYEE SELF-ESTEEM
A STUDY OF A NATURAL GAS DISTRIBUTION COMPANY IN GEORGIA**

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Abstract

The recent technological, economic and innovative developments have reshaped the long-established business models. Organizational change is now an important component of tactical plans for most businesses, leading to both new threats and potential prospects. The surge in the adoption of technologies marks a decisive shift towards digital transformation. This compels organizations to recalibrate their processes, objectives, and overarching missions to remain competitive. However, digital change often brings with it feelings of uncertainty, stress and concerns about job security. The study seeks to bridge the knowledge gap concerning the relationship between an employee's intrinsic motivation and affective commitment during such transformations. A theoretical model outlines predictors of employee intrinsic motivation, including perceived job characteristics and employee self-esteem. The paper reveals that job characteristics during digital transformation, along with employee self-esteem, positively influence intrinsic motivation, which in turn affects affective commitment.

Keywords: Intrinsic motivation, affective commitment, digital transformation, change, employee self-esteem, job characteristics.

I. Introduction

“Change is an organizational reality” (Robbins & Coulter, 2018, p. 208). Almost every enterprise undergoes change at some point to remain competitive. Firms initiate organizational changes to pursue progress and ensure success. Changes in business performance, industry standards, governmental policies, and other environmental factors can significantly influence a company's direction. Organizational change encompasses modifications in key elements like structure, culture, model, leadership, and more (Carnall, 1986). Implementing change can facilitate the successful adoption of new processes within a business, enhancing its efficiency. Pursuing innovative ideas, fostering skill development, and opening new opportunities underline the significance of organizational change.

The growing reliance on digital technologies has led to essential movements in organizational activities. “The adoption of social media, the internet of things (IoT), cloud computing, artificial intelligence, robotics, and big data analytics has transformed how businesses operate, helping in creating value and offering novel experiences to all stakeholders” (Goswami, 2019, p. 1023). By integrating these elements, management embarks on digital transformation. Such a change has become essential for certain enterprises to stay competitive in a dynamic environment. As a result, traditional business models often become obsolete and ill-equipped to address new challenges and opportunities.

To adapt to these emerging realities and remain competitive, companies must incorporate and leverage these digital technologies (Johansson, 2008). Digital

transformation is an ongoing process that guides institutions from their current status quo to a more advanced one. Fitzgerald (2013) defined it as “the process of using digital technologies to create new—or modify existing—business processes, culture, and customer experiences to meet shifting business and market requirements” (p.16). This transformation aims to produce organizational functions that are agile, innovative, people-focused, customer-centric, and restructured to meet new realities.

However, the execution of digital is fraught with challenges. Over 60% of companies fail to achieve their desired organizational alteration due to inappropriate integrations. Employee adaptation to change is deemed a crucial requirement within this transformational process. “Given that employees exhibit varied receptiveness to different forms of change, it's unsurprising to observe responses like mistrust (Gardner, 1998, pp. 48-70), entrenched attitudes (Schein, 1996, pp. 229-240), non-participation (Coch, 1948), and fear of the unknown. (Dawson, 1994) mentions, resistance to organizational transformation can stem from factors like changes in job skills, decreased economic security, psychological threats, disrupted social arrangements, and reduced status. This underscores the challenge HR practitioners face: crafting an environment where employees embrace, rather than resist to change” (Iverson, 1996, pp. 122-149)

The human element is pivotal during digital change. This transformational process impacts the attitudes and behaviors of employees across individual, team, and strategic levels. How does digital transfor-

mation affect employee attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors? Such changes often usher in new roles while simultaneously introducing uncertainties, which can trigger negative reactions among staff. Transformation can be perceived as a threat, leading to heightened "resistance to change." Various concerns drive people's resistance towards transformation, including fear of job instability, the transition from routine to new expectations, personal anxieties, and doubts about the change's benefit for the organization.

The ongoing technological evolution raises concerns about the extent to which advanced technologies might modify current roles or potentially render some jobs obsolete (Acemoglu, 2011; Frey, 2013). The influence of digitalization on labor has been presented by job reductions due to automation and digital shifts (Arntz, 2017). Yet, many scholars anticipate digital technologies to pave the way for novel job types and roles in the future. We can already observe the impact of digital transformation across various sectors. While there's extensive literature discussing potential shifts digital technology may usher in, there remains a gap regarding people's responses to such disruptions. As reliance on technology deepens during transformation, organizations increasingly need motivated individuals—those exhibiting positive responses—for successful task execution. Thus, heightening employee motivation is paramount for seamless and successful transformation (Choi, 1995, pp. 607-624)

Improperly executed changes can demoralize those responsible for implementation, leading to heightened stress levels. Stress profoundly influences employee behavior during transformation. Both personal traits and work-related factors are potential reasons for stress. "Any form of change, whether personal or job-related, can induce stress due to the inherent demands, constraints, or opportunities. Such stressors can range from pressure to avoid errors to challenging interactions with colleagues" (Robbins & Coulter, 2018, p. 222). Five primary job-related stressors are identified as task, role, interpersonal demands, organizational structure, and leadership style. Individual stressors encompass familial issues, financial concerns, and personality trait differences. Stress symptoms, manifesting as feelings of unhappiness, despondency, depression or general discontent, vary based on the causes, stemming from physical, psychological, or behavioral changes.

Broadly, change management research has endeavored to pinpoint primary reasons for potential change failures. A staggering 60% of organizations don't realize their transformational goals due to ineffective integration (Seeger, 2005). Such failures not only drain financial resources but also deteriorate employee morale and commitment, leading to diminished performance and heightened attrition (Eby, 2000). Numerous

studies have gravitated towards understanding "how recipients of change react to organizational shifts" (Oreg, 2011). Central to employees' roles during the change is their response to it (Armenakis, 1993, pp. 681-703). However, considering the pivotal role motivation occupies in change management, there's a noticeable breach in literature regarding the interplay between employee intrinsic motivation and affective commitment amidst change. To better understand the complexities of employee behavior during digital transformation, this study aims to explore specific factors that influence intrinsic motivation and their subsequent impact on affective commitment.

The current research endeavors to conceptualize a model delineating the factors of employee internal motivation, such as new job characteristics and employee self-esteem during the digital transformation. This study aspires to analyze the impact of intrinsic motivation on employee affective change commitment in Georgian natural gas distribution company. A primary objective of this paper is to identify the factors influencing intrinsic motivation and to elucidate the connection between motivation and commitment. To provide comprehensive insights into the interplay between these variables, the following research questions have been framed and will be rigorously explored throughout the study.

Given the gap in existing research, this study seeks to answer the following questions. The main question focuses on how employee affective commitment is affected by intrinsic motivation while implementing digital change. Therefore, sub questions are analyzing the effects of antecedents - job characteristics and employee self-esteem- on employee motivation.

Questions:

Q1. How is employee affective commitment influenced by intrinsic motivation during digital transformation?

Q2. How do perceived job characteristics influence employee motivation?

Q3. In what ways does employee self-esteem impact employee motivation?

Building on these research questions, the study proposes the following hypotheses to empirically investigate the relationships between intrinsic motivation, job characteristics, employee self-esteem, and affective commitment during digital change. The research postulates that intrinsic motivation significantly influences employee affective commitment, and the antecedents positively correlate with motivation during the tech-centric transformation.

Hypotheses:

H1: During digital transformation, there is a positive correlation between employee intrinsic motivation and affective commitment.

H2: Job characteristics positively affect employee intrinsic motivation in the context of digital transformation.

H3: Employee self-esteem exerts a positive influence on intrinsic motivation during such transformation.

II. Literature Review

To contextualize these hypotheses within existing knowledge, the following section reviews relevant literature on digital transformation, intrinsic motivation, and affective commitment.

A. Digital Transformation and Change Management

The 21st century has brought about significant disruptions that have reshaped the competitive landscape for businesses across various industries (Handfield, 2016). Technological innovations, financial crises, and global events like pandemics have introduced both unprecedented challenges and opportunities. These disruptions have intensified market volatility, compelling organizations to reevaluate their structures, processes, and core values in order to maintain competitiveness (Johansson, 2008). For instance, since 2016, a natural gas distribution company has been actively leveraging a digital strategy aimed at capitalizing on emerging opportunities and enhancing customer service. The utilities sector, in particular, is evolving rapidly, driven by market dynamics and the adoption of innovative technologies (Burton-Jones, 2020). Regulatory bodies are increasingly advocating for smarter, eco-friendly operational standards, while technology firms are entering the market with advanced analytical tools. These developments, though challenging, present considerable opportunities for digital transformation, pushing utilities toward comprehensive digitalization.

In times of disruption, the role of change management becomes critical for ensuring businesses can adapt effectively and maintain market relevance. Change management involves the strategic coordination of significant shifts across IT systems, business processes, and organizational structures, aimed at maximizing the benefits of change while mitigating associated risks (Murthy, 2021). Successful change management requires fostering a supportive environment characterized by strong leadership, clear communication channels, and a workforce that is receptive to change.

b. Employee Affective Commitment

Over the past several decades, research has increasingly focused on understanding employee commitment during periods of organizational change (Mathieu, 1990; Meyer, 2012; Kotter, 1996). Employee commitment is often reflected in behaviors such as punctuality, voluntary collaboration, team cohesion, goal achievement, and a genuine concern for the organization's well-being (Blau, 1993; Johnson, 2006). This commitment fosters an enthusiasm that drives employees to perform at higher levels. According to Allen (1996), employee commitment represents a psychological bond that discourages voluntary turnover. Robbins (2006) expands on this, viewing commitment as the strength of an individual's attachment to the organization's goals, with higher levels of commitment indicating deeper dedication.

Ibragimov et al. (2023) further explain that affective commitment (AC) is characterized by a desire to stay within an organization, demonstrated through cooperation and loyalty. Employees with affective commitment are motivated to contribute positively to their

organization's success. In contrast, normative commitment (NC) is based on a sense of obligation to remain, while continuance commitment (CC) reflects the perceived costs of leaving the organization (Mathieu, 1990). The effects of these different types of commitment vary: affective commitment is generally associated with positive outcomes, while continuance commitment can have negative implications (Porter, 1979; Becker, 1992; Herscovitch, 2002).

The significance of employee commitment during times of organizational change cannot be overstated. Recent advancements in smart technologies have fundamentally altered job dynamics, heightening employee concerns about the sustainability and relevance of their roles (Westerman, 2014). These concerns, coupled with fears of downsizing and the challenges of adapting to new digital norms, have placed employee motivation at the forefront of successful organizational adaptation. A motivated workforce is often linked to higher levels of commitment, and as Mathieu (1990) observed, increased motivation enhances the likelihood of strong commitment.

C. Employee Intrinsic Motivation.

Employee motivation has consistently been a dominant factor within organizational contexts for several decades (Howard, 2016; Amabile, 1993; Battistelli, 2013). Galetta (2013) defined motivation as an internal energy, a willingness that propels initiatives forward to realize anticipated results. Ahluwalia, (2019) describe it more succinctly: "Motivation is the intrinsic force within an individual that drives behavior in a deliberate and goal-oriented manner". Thus, when motivation originates internally, it often manifests as behavior aimed at achieving satisfaction. As a result, employees who are profoundly motivated become goal-centric, productive, and staunchly committed pillars within their organizations

Historically, psychological and business research have highlighted two types of employee motivation, categorizing it into intrinsic and extrinsic forms. This demarcation arises from varied individual expectations related to accomplishments, reward mechanisms, and the nature of task execution (Porter, 1968; McClelland, 1985; Maslow, 1987). Intrinsic motivation originates from an individual's inherent drive to engage in work and create something for the organization. It is described by factors such as internal growth opportunities, added responsibilities, flexible work schedules, emotional bonds with the job, and the freedom to exercise discretion in their roles. As articulated by (Gagné, 2005) "Intrinsic motivation is characterized by individuals engaging in an activity primarily because they find it inherently fascinating and derive genuine satisfaction from the activity itself."

Conversely, extrinsic motivation is fueled by external factors or tangible rewards. It revolves around the connection between an activity and its subsequent rewards, whether they be materialistic or verbal recognition. Here, the primary drive for individuals is not the activity itself but rather extrinsic consequences to which activity leads. Such motivators might encompass awards, prize, financial bonuses, or other tangible recognitions, propelling individuals to produce desired outcomes (Dörnyei, 2013; Locke, 1991; Elliot, 2005).

Motivation in a workplace context is related to a set of factors that orchestrate behavioral patterns within an organization (Sinani, 2016). Therefore, it is not a constant phenomenon and could change based on various internal and external factors (Lawler, 1973; Herzberg, 2017; Amabile, 1993). Aspects like technological advancements, shifts in organizational constructs, evolving work paradigms, job stability, and the introduction of novel operational processes have pronounced impacts on an individual's motivational levels. In our focal context, organizational change—specifically digital transformation—leads to technological replacements, new digitalized workflows, and profoundly shapes employee behavior. Gholizade (2014) posited that work motivation is a dynamic process, one that can change, influencing both the consistent behavior and emotional state of an employee.

Both leader and follower motivation determine the success of an initiative. Employees who are intrinsically motivated display a higher commitment to goals and, consequently, achieve better outcomes. Many authors have highlighted specific antecedents that can affect motivation in the workplace, including employee self-esteem, perceived job characteristics, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), trust and leader-member exchange (Prebensen, 2013; Perry, 2008).

D. Perceived Job Characteristics

The concept of job satisfaction has garnered significant attention since the 1950s, with early investigations spearheaded by Frederick Herzberg. Job satisfaction is closely related to work motivation. The higher the level of job satisfaction, the more motivated employees are likely to be. Smith et al. (1983) and Locke (1991) defined job satisfaction as a positive emotional response to one's job. This satisfaction arises from the fulfillment of job responsibilities and the perceived value created for organizations. Numerous studies examining job modifications focus on job enrichment and enlargement, with the aim of directly improving employee attitudes and performance. Technological innovations are significant drivers of change in job designs. Such innovations can significantly alter work structures, which, in turn, impact motivation and satisfaction (Kornhauser, 1965; Lawler, 1969).

In today's evolving business landscape, the necessity for motivated employees who harness their full potential for organizational benefit cannot be understated. The structure and organization of a job play a pivotal role in this context (Sever, 2019, p. 55). The way jobs are structured and organized has a profound influence on core organizational behavior factors, a sentiment echoed in previous studies (Judge, 2017). To enhance internal work motivation, it's essential to meticulously design jobs. As highlighted by (Gagné, 2005), jobs should offer a mix of variety, a sense of completion, and create a positive ripple effect in the lives of others. Furthermore, jobs should grant employees significant autonomy and discretion, coupled with constructive and meaningful feedback (p. 352, 2018). This structured approach ensures not just individual growth but also fosters organizational development.

E. Employee Self Esteem.

For many years, psychological scientists have explored the connection between an individual's intrinsic qualities of traits and capabilities to manage both internal and external environments. An employee's ability to navigate changes, specifically technological interventions within organizations, is important for future success. (Judge, 2001), and Locke (1991) introduced the "Core Self-Evaluation framework" (CSE) to explain human behavior and predict its potential impact on satisfaction and motivation. These scientists perceived CSE as a representation of a "fundamental, foundational assessment that people make concerning their worthiness, competence, and capabilities" (Kittinger, 2020, p. 68). They integrated the notion of CSE, which represents positive self-concept, into practice by investigating the unique distinctions in personal traits that lead to varied levels of individual and organizational outcomes (Judge, 1998; Judge, 2000).

CSE is understood as an aggregate of four conceptually related traits. These personal characteristics encompass self-esteem, self-efficacy, emotional stability, and locus of control. The CSE construct significantly influences an employee's ability to cope with uncertainty, complexity, and other potential challenges during periods of change (Judge, 2001). Researchers suggest that individuals with high self-esteem, elevated self-efficacy, an internal locus of control, and emotional stability tend to be more motivated and produce optimal job performance (Judge, 1998; Bandura, 2013; Spector, 1982). Numerous other studies have been conducted to investigate the possible influences of employee CSE in the workplace.

Several scholars have examined the relationship between the components of CSE and the Big Five model. All these studies show that CSE self-esteem accounts for major correlations with the five personality traits. "These four traits share a great deal of theoretical similarity because each of them describes a component of a common core" (Judge, (2001); Erez, (2001); and Bono, (2003) extended previous research and concluded that a person's personal assessment will help him cope with an uncertain environment. They emphasized the employee's ability, shaped by positive self-esteem, will help to overcome job complexity and achieve higher levels of motivation. Therefore, the author aims to use the measurement of self-esteem and study its impact on employee intrinsic motivation. on behalf of the entire CSE construct.

Figure 1.1. depicts the relationship between employee intrinsic motivation and employee affective commitment to achieve the efficient implementation of digital transformation and change management within the organizations (See Figure 1.1.). Two key factors are believed to affect the degree of motivation towards digitalization: job characteristics perceived by employees and their self-esteem. Employee positive self-evaluation and perception of new tasks and requirements set the foundation for efficient change management and is a composite of available knowledge, past experiences and clear communication.

III. Methodology

The study employs quantitative research design method to comprehensively explore the potential relationships between variables. Statistical data were collected from 411 respondents through an online survey distributed to 678 employees from various divisions and departments of a gas distribution company involved in or managing digital transformation processes in Georgia. A link to 20 survey questions, prepared in Microsoft Forms and describing the influence of prior motivation on employee commitment, was sent to each participant. To make sure that the least required number of respondents will be acquired, the reminder information has been sent to them by email.

Variables were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." Data analysis was conducted using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to interpret the relationships between variables. These statistical techniques were chosen to validate the model's significance in measuring the relationships between variables. The analysis was performed using Statistical Software for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and SmartPLS.

The statistical model comprises two components. The first component predicts the relationship between independent variables, such as perceived job character-

istics and employee self-esteem, and the dependent variable, intrinsic motivation. The second component examines the influence of intrinsic motivation, as an independent variable, on the dependent variable, affective commitment. It is hypothesized that the effects observed in the first model (motivation) will similarly impact employee commitment during digital transformation.

IV. Findings

Having outlined the quantitative research design and statistical methods employed to explore the relationships between variables, we now present the findings from the data analysis to assess how these relationships manifest in the context of employee motivation and commitment during digital transformation.

Normality Test by Shapiro-Wilk Test:

The study failed the normality test for each of the variables, as indicated by the Shapiro-Wilk test results, which yielded a p-value of 0.00 for all variables analyzed. A p-value greater than 0.05 is required to demonstrate that the data is normally distributed. This means that the Shapiro-Wilk test shows, with 95% confidence, that we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the distribution of the data is statistically different from a normal distribution. The failure could be due to the presence of categorical variables (using a 5-point Likert scale). Given the failed normality test, regression analysis may not be appropriate (see Table 1).

Table 1.

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Intrinsic Motivation	.126	411	.000	.963	411	.000
Perceived Job Characteristics	.121	411	.000	.945	411	.000
Employee Self Esteem	.100	411	.000	.972	411	.000
Employee Affective Commitment	.087	411	.000	.978	411	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Homogeneity Test:

Another assumption tested was the equality of variance. The study needed to confirm that all variables have equal variances to proceed with the ANOVA analysis. The results show that we could not reject the null hypothesis with 95% confidence for any of the variables. Therefore, all variables tested have statistically equal variances (see Tables 2-3-4).

Table 2.

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances^{a,b}

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Intrinsic Motivation	Based on Mean	1.868	9	401	.055
	Based on Median	1.414	9	401	.180
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.414	9	360.093	.180
	Based on trimmed mean	1.693	9	401	.089

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.

a. Dependent variable: Intrinsic Motivation

b. Design: Intercept + JOBCH

Table 3.

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances^{a,b}

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Intrinsic Motivation	Based on Mean	1.381	10	400	.186
	Based on Median	1.620	10	400	.098
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.620	10	364.357	.099
	Based on trimmed mean	1.419	10	400	.169

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.

a. Dependent variable: Intrinsic Motivation

b. Design: Intercept + SLFEST

Table 4.

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances^{a,b}

			Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Employee	Affective	Based on Mean	.419	10	400	.937
Commitment		Based on Median	.326	10	400	.974
		Based on Median and with adjusted df	.326	10	388.926	.974
		Based on trimmed mean	.420	10	400	.937

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.

a. Dependent variable: Employee Affective Commitment

b. Design: Intercept + INMOT

□

ANOVA Testing:

Based on these results, it was decided to proceed with ANOVA testing using the following models:

- Identify the significant influence of perceived job characteristics and employee self-esteem on the dependent variable, intrinsic motivation.
- Identify the significant influence of intrinsic motivation on the dependent variable, affective commitment.

ANOVA Analysis: Job Characteristics and Intrinsic Motivation:

The SPSS tables indicate that both tests have a significance level of 0.000. Thus, with 95% confidence,

we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the means are statistically different. The study found that perceived job characteristics (JOBCH) and employee self-esteem (SLFEST) have statistically significant effects on the dependent variable, motivation.

ANOVA Analysis: Motivation and Employee Affective Commitment:

After establishing that motivation is affected by the factors mentioned above, we proceeded to examine the statistical significance between the dependent variable, employee affective commitment, and motivation. The ANOVA test confirmed that there is statistical significance in this relationship (see Tables 5-6-7).

Table 5.

Intrinsic Motivation					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	43.686	9	4.854	29.564	.000
Within Groups	65.840	401	.164		
Total	109.527	410			

Table 6.

Intrinsic Motivation					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.505	10	1.251	5.156	.000
Within Groups	97.021	400	.243		
Total	109.527	410			

ANOVA

Employee Affective Commitment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	10.002	10	1.000	2.882	.002
Within Groups	138.817	400	.347		
Total	148.819	410			

V. Limitations

One of the main limitations of this study relates to the self-assessment nature of the employee questionnaires. The resulting data may contain biased information and inaccuracies. Due to various individual and organizational factors, respondents might withhold truthful information and provide socially desirable answers. Leader-member exchange or social exchange relationships can create a sense of obligation among employees to repay their managers or the company with positive responses and a willingness to support change. Furthermore, some words and expressions in the survey questions were unclear to the respondents, leading to misunderstandings. Although the survey questions were translated into Georgian, words such as 'intrinsic,' 'affective,' 'commitment,' and 'digitalization' may still lack direct equivalents in the local language.

Moreover, some participants may not have had sufficient information about the transformation process, the shared vision, and the overall benefits of digitalization. Another limitation concerns the sample selection and methodology used during the survey. A large sample size of employees might have randomly selected answers, which could affect the test results. Conducting a study using focus groups consisting of employees who understand the process and recognize its significance for the organization's well-being, selected through judgmental sampling, could provide different insights. Judgmental sampling, a form of non-probability sampling, involves participants being chosen by the researcher in a predetermined manner. A focus group of approximately 50 employees could yield more reliable and robust information about the process.

Another important consideration is that the results obtained at a particular point in time may change in the future. Therefore, periodic evaluations are necessary to track ongoing changes, or the survey should be repeated after the full completion of the digitalization process, which is planned to be finished by 2027. Finally, there may be other antecedents of intrinsic motivation that were not addressed in this study.

VI. Future Research

Given the importance of the impact of digital transformation on employees, further research is needed to explore the direct effect of perceived job characteristics and employee self-esteem on their affective commitment during the change. Employees with a transformed mindset are likely to be more engaged and will show positive results. Moreover, assuming that

transformation will be a long-term process, future research should investigate the influence of employee satisfaction and motivation on employee performance once digital integration is completed.

Considering the advancement of digital technologies in different business areas such as healthcare, hospitality, retail, finance and manufacturing, future investigations could focus on one of these environments. For instance, digitalization in healthcare aims to minimize the organizational burden and other monotonous jobs that healthcare employees currently execute. Consequently, these professionals could devote more time to working with and observing patients. In hospitality sector digital processes help to organize operations, allow customization and get useful information out of the collected data for future proactive decision making. In manufacturing, digital tools enhance efficiency, improve quality control, and enable the design of more desirable goods and services. Therefore, future research could focus on implementing similar digital advancements in the healthcare industry, examining how levels of motivation influence commitment during this type of digital transformation.

VI. Urgency and Contribution

Change management, individual motivation, and employee commitment are important constructs across a range of organizational structures, acting as a barometer for measuring organizational commitment and motivation levels. This research aims to provide a new perspective for both academia and practitioners by highlighting the interaction between motivation and commitment during times of change. The findings of this study could benefit consultancies and training firms, by equipping organizations on the verge of technological transformation. Furthermore, this research may establish a foundation for subsequent investigations into digital transformations, introducing unique research questions and hypotheses.

VII. Conclusion

Technological disruptions bring unique opportunities to the market, which are crucial for the competitiveness of any organization. Consequently, these institutions must adapt their traditional business models to introduce innovation, enhance efficiency, and elevate the quality of existing products and services. Innovation is inevitable, but also challenging. Employees can be both the main obstacle in the process and the key to success. Their resistance or openness to change signif-

icantly influences the course of events. The way employees perceive the transformation shapes their attitudes and behavior.

Researchers argue that digitalization requires motivating people to achieve their goals and objectives. The internal drive inherent in everyone allows each professional to go beyond expected responsibilities and create a connection to the organization's interests and overall well-being, thereby promoting affective commitment to change. The research examined how perceptions of new job requirements and employee self-evaluation may impact internal motivation, and how this motivation subsequently influences affective commitment during the transformation

Digital change introduces new job characteristics and techniques to complete tasks, which necessitates knowledge, skills, and experience. These competencies form a strong foundation for self-esteem, an individual's evaluation of their self-worth. An employee's ability to navigate change also relies on a sense of trust within the organization and among colleagues. When there is a proven sense of trust, employees feel secure, rely on their teammates' support, and experience increased motivation, leading to emotional commitment. Thus, when employees believe that digital change can benefit their organization, they are more likely to collaborate effectively as team members and work towards common goals.

Intrinsic motivation is an influential factor in pushing leaders and subordinates to achieve. A leader's motivation influences follower motivation during change. Strong leadership support opens up opportunities for effective use of resources, communication, and information sharing.

Digitalization requires the participation of all employees at the individual, team and managerial levels. This process is well known in companies in manufacturing, retail, hospitality and healthcare, as it brings efficiency, product innovation and data analytics. For utilities, especially for natural gas distribution companies, it is crucial for improving customer experience and ensuring progress.

The research design employed quantitative methods, utilizing a survey. The survey was sent to 687 employees and 411 responses were collected. Statistical data faced issues with normal distribution but passed the homogeneity tests, providing a basis for conducting ANOVA analysis. Perceived job characteristics and self-esteem were found to have a significant relationship with intrinsic motivation, which was later found to have an influence on change commitment.

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